

Biodiversity and regulatory ecosystem services in soybean (*Glycine max*) cropping systems

Daniel A. Amthauer Gallardo^{*±1}, Georg Everwand², Heinz Stichnothe³, Jens Dauber¹

¹ Thünen Institute of Biodiversity

² Bavarian State Ministry of the Environment and Consumer Protection

³ Thünen Institute of Agricultural Technology

* Speaker

± Corresponding author: [daniel.amthauer\[at\]thuenen.de](mailto:daniel.amthauer[at]thuenen.de)

1 Introduction

The soybean, belonging to the legume family (Fabaceae), plays a key role in many cropping systems and is today the most important oil seed crop, securing food and feed supply around the world. The area cropped with soybean worldwide has more than tripled from 37.5 million hectares in 1974 to around 117.5 million hectares in 2018. To date, Europe strongly depends on imported protein crops, mainly soybeans and soybean products, to feed livestock and for human consumption (Watson et al. 2017). This dependence has led to increased deforestation in soybean producing countries. Moreover, nutrient import resulted in a strong eutrophication of intensive European agroecosystems. To reduce this dependence and the environmental impacts, the European Union (EU) encourages European farmers to grow more leguminous crops, such as soybean, faba bean (*Vicia faba*), pea (*Pisum sativum*) or lupin (e.g. *Lupinus albus*, *L. angustifolius* or *L. luteus*). Currently the EU and many of its members promote legume cropping with several programs.

Most legumes host rhizobium bacteria that fix nitrogen (N) and thus do not need N fertilizer. Many have deep and extensive root systems, produce large amounts of nitrogen rich crop residues and possess a flowering system that can facilitate insect pollination. Due to these key qualities, it is supposed that legumes offer numerous regulatory environmental services and effects on biodiversity: reduction of adverse N-emissions, mitigation of CO₂ emissions, better energy balance of cropping systems, soil fertility including improvement of nutrient mobilization from deeper soil layers as well as improvement of soil structure and porosity and provisioning of habitat and resources for fauna above- and belowground (Everwand et al. 2017). Nevertheless, to this time it is not established whether and to which extent soybean-based cropping systems offer regulatory ecosystem services or enhance biodiversity. This literature study aims to determine the effect of the soybean crop and its cropping systems i) on communities of plant, arthropods and birds, specifically their species richness, diversity, abundance and biomass; ii) on ecosystem services, such as pest control, pollination and soil fertility and iii) on management intensity, crop rotation and landscape parameters as drivers of biodiversity.

2 Materials and Methods

The literature survey yielded 60 studies, published between 1983 and 2018, which report on impacts of soybean cropping or soybeans in cropping systems on biodiversity in comparison to other crops or cropping systems without soybean. We excluded studies on fungi, soil meso-, and microorganisms and found 21 studies including plants, 40 studies including invertebrates and 6 studies including vertebrates, all of which were birds. The studied parameters were mainly abundance or biomass with 51 studies. Species richness or diversity and community composition were included in 29 and 23 studies, respectively. Effects on ecosystem services, such as pollination or pest control were investigated in 22 of the studies. Landscape effects were included in 23 of the studies. The geographic focus of the studies was on the American continent, with 38 studies from USA, 7 from Canada and 9 from Argentina. A comparison of different crops is shown in 35 studies and 49 studies compare different cropping systems.

3 Results

We found reports of potential benefits of soybean cropping on plants, pollinators, parasitoids and other natural pest control agents. Though weed species richness was the same, weed abundance and biomass were commonly higher in soy than in other crops. At the same time, soy, especially in low input systems, showed higher predator and herbivore insect species richness (Adams et al. 2017). Those, however, were in most

▶ [Back to "Table of Contents"](#)

studies also strongly influenced by landscape composition, field size, crop diversity and rotation, as well as management measures, such as tillage regime, fertilizer and pesticide inputs. Most studies show that biodiversity parameters are affected by crops or cropping sequences or management such as tillage, crop protection or fertilizer regime.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

We founded higher weed abundance and biomass but no higher diversity. It appears that the provided resources from soy cultivation to soil (nitrogen fixation and improved soil porosity) positively affects the agroecosystem but the plant diversity is already limited by the kind of artificial ecosystem itself and the agricultural management practices applied. We confirmed our assumption that arthropod richness and biomass is increased by soy cultivation, presumably through nutrient and protein rich foliar biomass.

We conclude that an assessment of potential biodiversity and ecosystem service effect of soybean in cropping systems cannot be founded on plant traits of soybean alone. Soil management and plant protection measures of the entire soybean-based crop rotation have to be taken into account as well as the structure of the landscape in which the respective cropping system is embedded.

Acknowledgments

This study is part of the EU Project Legumes Translated.

References

- Watson, C.A., M. Reckling, S. Preissel, J. Bachinger, G. Bergkvist, T. Kuhlman, K. Lindström, T. Nemecek, C.F.E. Topp, A. Vanhatalo, P. Zander, D. Murphy-Bokern, and F.L. Stoddard. 2017. Grain legume production and use in European agricultural systems. *Advances in Agronomy* 144, 236-303.
- Everwand G., S. Cass, J. Dauber, M. Williams and J.C. Stout. 2017. Legume crops and biodiversity. In: D. Murphy- Bokern, F.L. Stoddard and C.A. Watson (eds) *Legumes in cropping systems*. Wallingford: CAB International, pp 55-69
- Adams, I. I. I. P. R., D. B. Orr, C. Arellano, and Y. J. Cardoza. 2017. Soil and Foliar Arthropod Abundance and Diversity in Five Cropping Systems in the Coastal Plains of North Carolina. *Environmental Entomology* 46:771-783.